

Ternary Complex—Influence of Oxalic Acid on Vanadium(V) Determination with 4-Sulpho-2-Aminobenzenethiol in Aqueous Solution

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Vanadium(V) forms a ternary blue violet complex with oxalic acid and 4-sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol. The complex is formed in the concentration range of 0.24 M to 0.64 M hydrochloric acid. It absorbs maximum at 560 nm and is stable for 5 hr at room temperature. The system obeys Beer's law from 1 to 36 ppm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity values are $1.6 \times 10^5 \text{ l. mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0302 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{ V(V)}$. A 50-fold excess of Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Bi(III), Sn(II), Pb(II), Ti(IV), Mo(VI), W(VI), U(VI) and tartrate, fluoride, acetate, citrate, EDTA, oxalate do not interfere. The mixed-ligand complex is formed in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio of V : oxal : thiol. The overall stability constant of the vanadium complex is $6.40 \pm 1^\circ$. The photometric method has been found to be very selective in presence of titanium(IV) and other metal ions. Iron(III) and iron(II) strongly interfered.

A number of aryl hydroxamic acids¹⁻⁴ have been used as analytical reagents for the estimation of vanadium in materials and matrices. The formation of vanadium complexes of variable composition at varying conditions of pH and acidities⁵ indicated the potential complexing power of the reagents. The selectivity of the methods described earlier in a review⁶ and a monograph⁷ is limited due to interferences by iron(III)/iron(II) and titanium(IV). The tolerance limits with sequestering agents and prior separation are not effectively high enough. Some ternary procedures provide very high sensitivity, but are less selective for the separation and determination of vanadium(V) in presence of small amounts of Ti(IV). The use of oxalic acid as the mixed ligand component for vanadium determination by the ternary procedure involving either solvent extraction or aqueous medium are not reported earlier.

Oxalic acid, which forms 5-coordinate neutral oxalate complexes, acts as a bidentate ligand to give a ternary complex reported in this paper. It reacts with many transition metal ions such as Hg(II), Pd(II), Cr(VI), Os(VIII) to give useful analytical methods of determination. Vanadium(V) has been determined in purely aqueous medium with high selectivity and without the use of any reducing agent. Selective complex formation and masking action of oxalate ion is the basis of a spectrophotometric method of determination in presence of excess of Ti(IV) and other ions, but iron(III) strongly interferes.

Experimental

Apparatus: A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells was used for absorbance

measurements. A Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer was used for recording the IR spectra of the reagent.

Reagents: Ammonium vanadate (E. Merck) was dissolved in water containing a few drops of ammonia and standardized to give 0.1 mg/ml solution of the metal^{7,8}. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their analytical grade salts. All other chemicals and solvents were of A. R. quality.

4-Sulpho-2-aminobenzenethiol: Distilled 2-aminobenzenethiol was sulphonated^{9,10} by slow and dropwise addition to sulphuric acid at 5°. The mixture was stirred thoroughly for 30 min and the thick mass was added to ice-water. The compound was recrystallized to give needle-shaped crystals (m.p. 190°). 1.0% aqueous solutions of reagent and oxalic acid were used for the ternary system.

General procedure: An aliquot of standard vanadium(V) solution was mixed with 5 ml of 1.0% reagent solution, 5 ml of 1.0% oxalic acid and 2 ml of 4 M hydrochloric acid in a 25 ml volumetric flask. The mixture was kept for half-an-hour with occasional shaking. The volume was made up with double distilled water. The reaction mixture was mixed thoroughly at room temperature. The reagent blank prepared similarly showed no absorbance. The absorbance of the blue-violet complex was measured at 560 nm against water blank.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectrum: Both the binary and ternary complex systems showed similar absorption in the visible region. The ternary complex (violet)

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absorbs maximum at 560 nm when measured against water blank (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorbance curve.

- Binary complex, 16 ppm
- Ternary complex, 16 ppm.

Effect of acidity, reagent, time : The complex is formed at pH from 2.0 to 2.5. A flat maximum at 510-540 nm is obtained between pH 1.0 and 2.0. The complex is fully formed when the HCl concentration lies between 0.24 M and 0.64 M. 2 ml of 4M HCl was added for all measurements and the acid concentration was maintained at 0.32 M HCl.

It was found that 4-9 ml of 1.0% oxalic acid is sufficient for complete formation of the complex with 5 ml of 1.0% reagent. The colour is fully developed by using 0.1 to 10 ml of 1.0% oxalic acid. For a second series of solutions [V(V), 16 ppm] with 5 ml of 1.0% oxalic acid always added to it, the complex begins to form after the addition of 0.1 ml of 1.0% sulpho-thiol reagent. 2 ml of the reagent is sufficient for full colour development. A 5 ml of 1.0% reagent solution was always used. The ternary complex formation is independent of the order of addition of reagents.

Calibration curve, optimum range, photometric error and sensitivity : The system obeys Beer's law from 1-36 ppm of V(V). The optimum range of determination obtained by Ringbom's plot¹¹ was found to be 4-26 ppm. The per cent relative analysis error per 1% absolute photometric error was obtained following Ayres' equation¹² as 2.7%. The molar absorptivity of the ternary violet complex is 1.6×10^5 l.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and Sandell's sensitivity¹³ was calculated to be 0.0302 μ g cm⁻² V(V), respectively, at 560 nm.

Composition of the ternary complex : In most of the mixed-ligand systems a log-log method is found

necessary to determine the metal to ligand ratios in the complex¹⁴. In this particular system, the metal : ligand composition was directly determined in a complementary mixture of 12 ml volume. The V(V) : oxal ratio was determined using three different amounts (4, 6 and 8 ml) of an equimolar solution of reagent (R₂) as the fixed component. The complex was formed utilizing equimolar solutions (9.815 $\times 10^{-3}$ M) of vanadium(V) and oxalic acid (R₁) following the procedure at 560 nm and 570 nm. The plots of absorbance against M/(M+R₁) fraction of the metal showed a break at 1 : 1 (M : R₁) ratio (Fig. 2). Similarly, V(V) : sulpho-thiol ratio was determined using 12 ml mixture of equimolar solutions (9.815 $\times 10^{-3}$ M) of vanadium(V) and

Fig. 2. Continuous variation method.

- [M]=[R₁]=[R₂]=9.815 $\times 10^{-3}$ M
 ○ R₁=6 ml ○ =8 ml ● R₂=6 ml ● =8 ml

reagent (R₂) and correspondingly three varied amounts (4, 6 and 8 ml) of an equimolar oxalic acid solution (R₁) as the other fixed component. The plots of absorbance measured at 550-570 nm against M/(M+R₂) fraction of the metal showed a sharp break at 1 : 1 (M : R) ratio (Fig. 2) in all the experiments. Thus, a 1 : 1 : 1 (M : R₁ : R₂) composition was obtained for the complex by method of continuous variation. In mole-ratio method, studies with a fixed amount (4, 6 and 8 ml) of oxalic acid and a 12 ml mixture of equimolar solutions (9.815 $\times 10^{-3}$ M) of vanadium(V) and reagent (R₂) indicated a 1 : 1 (M : R₂) ratio at 550-570 nm (Fig. 3). Similarly, experiments with a fixed amount (4, 6 and 8 ml) of sulpho-thiol reagent and a 12 ml mixture of equimolar solutions (9.815 $\times 10^{-3}$ M) of vanadium(V) and oxalic acid (R₁) indicated a 1 : 1 (M : R₁) ratio at 550-570 nm (Fig. 3). The composition of the ternary complex (1 : 1 : 1 = M : R₁ : R₂) was verified by the mole-ratio method and

its formula may be assigned as $\text{VO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot (\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_5\text{S}_2)$.

Fig. 3. Molar-ratio method.

$[\text{M}] = [\text{R}_1] = [\text{R}_2] = 9.815 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$
 — $R_1 = 4 \text{ ml}$, $\circ R_1 = 6 \text{ ml}$;
 ● $R_2 = 4 \text{ ml}$, $\circ R_2 = 6 \text{ ml}$

Interference study: The tolerance limits with 0.2 mg of vanadium(V) were determined with 10 mg of diverse ions following the procedure at 0.32 M hydrochloric acid. 10 mg of Co(II), Ni(II), Mn(II), Sn(II), Pb(II), Zn(II), Al(III), Bi(III), Zr(IV), Ta(V), Mo(VI), W(VI), U(VI) or Cr(III) showed no interference. 5 mg of Cu(II), Cd(II), Re(VII), Ce(IV), Ti(I) or fluoride did not interfere. 10 mg of acetate, phosphate, ascorbate, sulphate, tartrate, citrate, EDTA are tolerated in the determination. Fe(III) or Cr(VI) strongly interferes. Hg(II), Pd(II), Cr(VI), CN^- , SCN^- present in 5 mg amount interfered in the determination. Ti(IV) showed no interference.

Degree of dissociation and stability constants: The formation constants of the ternary complex have been investigated by the photometric technique. The degree of dissociation (α) for $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ has been calculated from the relation

$$\alpha = A_m(0.690) - A_s(0.395) / A_m(0.690) = 0.4275$$

The stability constant of the complex has been calculated from the relation $K = 1/K' = 1 - \alpha/\alpha^2 c$, where c is the concentration of the complex. $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ has been found to be 3.30. Similarly, $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{ML}}$ has been found to be 3.10 ($\alpha = 0.3333$, $c = 6.28 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$). Almost equal stability value points to the simultaneous and successive complex formation in the vanadium chelate. Thus, the overall stability constant has been calculated to be 6.40 ($\log K = \log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}} + \log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{ML}}$) at $29 \pm 1^\circ$.

The violet ternary complex is extracted with *n*-butyl, *iso*-butyl, *n*-amyl and *iso*-amyl alcohols. Chloroform, benzene and carbon tetrachloride do not extract the complex due to the presence of a sulphonic acid group in the molecule.

No coloured complex is formed by VO(II) either in the presence or absence of oxalic acid. The vanadyl complex has a 5-coordinate structure with vanadyl oxygen at the top of a possible tetragonal pyramidal geometry. The sulpho-thiol reagent behaves here as a mono-protic bidentate ligand. A violet complex separates from the bulk solution after 24 hr at room temperature and is thermally stable.

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